

WORKSHOP 1: SYSTEMS MAPPING AND LEVERAGE POINTS

Date: 05.10.2023

Duration: 2.5 hours

Number of participants: 7 people

Profile of participants: Three peer-mentors living in or close to Oslo, Norway, aged 27-32 years, with experience from camps for children, youth, and adults with disabilities (all) and from serving on a political advisory board for people with disabilities (one). One young activity leader from OOF. Three social and natural science researchers from NINA.

Meeting agenda:

1. Short introduction to the PLANET4B project
2. Round of introduction, sharing a memory from a good nature experience
3. Mapping of challenges and possibilities for making outdoor nature recreation accessible to children with disabilities
4. Discussion around possible activities or interventions for making outdoor nature recreation more readily accessible to children with disabilities
5. Plan for future workshops and activities

1. Short introduction to the PLANET4B project

The first workshop began with welcoming everyone to the expert-network (aka learning community). One of the facilitators gave a brief overview of the EU project in general and specifically in Norway. She also talked about privacy and informed consent. All participants from outside the PLANET4B consortium were given consent forms that they signed and gave back to NINA.

2. Round of introduction, sharing a memory from a good nature experience

We had a short round of introductions where we shared some personal information and a memory from a nice nature experience.

The nature experiences that we shared had some common elements. They either involved shared moments in nature with family or friends, e.g. in front of a bonfire, or meetings with wild animals or beautiful scenery while being alone in nature. The nature could both be close by home, e.g. in the city of Oslo, or far away.

3. Mapping of challenges and possibilities for making outdoor nature recreation accessible to children with disabilities

A facilitator from NINA introduced the topic by talking a bit about free play versus organized outdoor nature recreational activities, presenting findings from personal research about why children are not spending much time outdoors these days. Some of the reasons include having too many things to do and too many organized activities to fit into their schedules. Additionally, parental concerns about safety (e.g., traffic safety) can be a barrier. However, access to outdoor areas is generally good.

To open the discussion the facilitator then asked the following questions: Why do so few people with disabilities take part in organized activities where people "without" disabilities participate? When outdoor nature recreations like the Norwegian Trekking Association, DNT, organise, for example, a moonlit walk, why are so few, if any, children with disabilities participating? The discussion that followed was allowed to flow freely and some of the thoughts that emerged are presented as bullets below.

- Safe environments are important, especially for children who have been injured. Children benefit from feeling a sense of belonging and from activities like making bread on a stick by the fire.

- Time, it takes more time to go out with children who have disabilities, and everyday life is busy. It's also important that activities don't necessarily need to happen quickly.
- Money for traveling to and participating in events. It can be expensive, especially when you have children with special needs. It costs more for children with disabilities to have the same experiences.
- Clear information about what to expect is also important for people to feel confident joining something new. Having a support system or someone to ask is crucial.
- Mindsets are important. Not everything needs to be "universally designed." Sometimes very little is required. It doesn't all have to be perfect. The most important thing is to try to facilitate, create opportunities for adjusting and finding solutions. When it comes to children, it's important to teach them how to handle the unexpected.
- Fear and insecurity often lead to a quick "no" from managers or staff when asked about accessibility, e.g., if a location is accessible for wheelchairs. Often when people answer "no", they might be afraid of making mistakes or worry about legal responsibility if something unexpected happens, such as a fire.
- Navigating the Norwegian welfare system (NAV) is challenging. Dealing with applications is a part-time job. How to describe/define what you are applying for is decisive and can result in refusal or permission. NAV has lists over aids, and you must start with the cheapest option, regardless of whether it is the most suitable option or not. Up to the age of 26, everything goes under NAV, after 26 years you must apply for money from an annual pot administered by NAV. In 2023, that money ended on 14 January.

4. Discussion around possible activities or interventions for making outdoor nature recreation more readily accessible to children with disabilities

- There is a need for a place to go to for information (very little aggregated common information) e.g., about offers in the municipalities or by outdoor nature recreation organisations. To have someone to ask e.g. about organised activities or how to navigate the NAV system would be a great help.
- The mentoring scheme is so ingenious that it might be the way to go to spread it. The Sunnaasstiftelsen trains around 30 mentors a year.
- Perhaps presenting and showing concretely what is needed to representatives from the municipality could be a way to put the challenges higher up on the political agenda?

5. Plan for future workshops and activities

Meeting minutes were compiled and shared with everyone for corrections and further input.

We decided to set up a digital meeting with Sunnaasstiftelsen to hear more about their experience from working with municipalities.

We decided to recruit two parents of children with disabilities into the expert network.

The next, in person workshop to continue the systems and leverage points mapping was set for December 5th 2023.

WORKSHOP 2: SYSTEMS MAPPING AND LEVERAGE POINTS (continued)

Date: 05.12.2023

Duration: 2.5 hours

Number of participants: 7 people

Profile of participants: Three peer-mentors living in or close to Oslo, Norway, one of them a parent of a child with disabilities, all with experience from camps for children, youth, or adults with disabilities. One young activity leader from OOF. Three social and natural science researchers from NINA.

Meeting agenda:

1. Welcome and summary of WS1 + digital meeting with Sunnaastiftelsen
2. Interactive systems mapping
3. Co-identification of actors to interact with/places to intervene for changing the system in desired direction (aka identification of leverage points)
4. Wrap-up and plan for future workshops and activities

1. Welcome and summary of WS1 + digital meeting with Sunnaastiftelsen

Everyone was welcomed and we had a short round of presentations for the newcomers. We quickly recapped the main points from the digital meeting with Sunnaastiftelsen where we had discussed their experience of working with municipalities. The said municipalities were clear on three things: they have (1) no time, (2) lack of specialist expertise, and (3) not enough resources. In conclusion, municipalities are very cumbersome to work with. We then quickly recapped the discussion points from the previous workshop, which led us to the next agenda point.

2. Interactive systems mapping

This was an interactive task. We had prepared an almost empty poster where the goal (mid-point) of the poster was that children with disabilities would have access to good nature experiences. We discussed a bit what good nature experiences could be for children with disabilities. These could include both short hikes/trips in the nearby nature, requiring small and simple means, and trips to places further away from the city. However, we found that defining what good nature experiences are was difficult. It could be very little and very much.

We were then got Post-it notes, pens, and stickers and were instructed to write down the names of actors/institutions/ regulations/elements that allow or limit/prevent children with disabilities from having access to good nature experiences. Once we had filled some post-it notes we started to place these around the goal (the children with access to good nature experience). In this process, as we could see what others had written on their post-its we also got reminded or inspired to write down additional actors and elements on new post-its that we added to the systems diagram.

Next, we arranged the post-its according to three different levels that we identified within our system (Fig. 1). Closest to our goal were interest organisations, private funds, private landowners and insurance companies. In the middle layer we placed institutions like the school, the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV), municipalities, and public funds. In the third and outermost layer we placed rules and regulations that “govern” the system.

Onion diagram workshop	
Core:	Children with disabilities do have access to nature experiences
Direct factors influencing case study (inner circle):	Sunnaasstiftelsen foundation Beitostølen og Valnesfjorden helsesportsenter (health sports centre) DNT (The Norwegian Trekking Association) Lars (The Norwegian Spinal Cord Injuries Association) LHL hjerneslag Ung (national association) Sparebankstiftelsen, Gjensidestiftelsen (support funds) Landowners Sports clubs (voluntary work) Insurances Adapted equipment Knowledge and attitudes Information Safe environment Will to make it happen Accessibility Flexibility in existing offers
Distal factors influencing case study (outer circle):	NAV (Norwegian labor and welfare administration) Municipality economy Council for people with disabilities School system Public subsidies for organisations that wants to include children and others with disabilities
Other distal factors influencing case study:	Attitudes (Stereotypical notions about outdoor recreation (friluftsliv) and disabilities) Friluftsløven (Outdoor recreation act) Allemannsretten (right to roam) Act relating to Motorised traffic on uncultivated land and in watercourses Laws/rules/regulations

Figure 1. The three levels identified in the Oslo recreational case system from the core (our goal) in dark green, through the outermost layer in light green.

3. Co-identification of actors to interact with/places to intervene for changing the system in desired direction (aka identification of leverage points)

After a short break we came back to the systems map over the different actors, institutions, regulations and elements. We then proceeded to put orange or heart-shaped stickers on the post-its, indication whether they represented barriers or enablers of our goal (access for children with disabilities to good nature experiences) to identify places in our system to intervene for desired changes to occur (Fig. 2).

The key obstacles identified and in need of change in our system were:

- Rules and regulations
- Lack of information
- Knowledge and attitudes
- Economy Accessibility
- Safe environment
- Lack of outdoor nature recreational activities on offer

Figure 2. The three-layered system map with orange and heart stickers indicating obstacles (places in need of change) and enablers of access to good nature experiences for children with disabilities.

Although most of the obstacles (orange stickers) were placed or identified in the middle layer of our system, e.g. with the municipalities, we also recognised that these were places where it would be difficult for us to intervene. With our expert network we therefore decided to focus on the inner layer where we could foresee having impact.

As an intervention we identified that sharing of knowledge among the actors of our system could help mitigate fear and insecurity and help make information available / improve flow of information (cf. barriers discussed in WS1). Increased knowledge would equip individuals to navigate the system more effectively, reducing the challenges involved in seeking support from for example NAV. Also, with increased knowledge, efforts could be made to enhance the availability of inclusive recreational options to reduce travel distances and increase opportunities for all children to participate in outdoor activities. This would support the development of children's skills in nature-based settings by understanding the importance of experience and challenges. Knowledge about the benefits of experiential learning in natural settings would help educators create opportunities for children to develop skills through hands-on experiences and thus breaking the cycle of fear and fostering growth and development.

To increase knowledge, we concluded that an intervention could be to build on the expert network that we were establishing. Thus far the network included the Norwegian institute for Nature research (NINA) and researchers, The Oslo Outdoor Recreational Council (OOF) and an activity leader, parents of children with acquired disabilities and young peer mentors with acquired disabilities. We concluded that expanding on our expert network to include outdoor nature recreation organisations could be a good intervention to break down the siloes between organisations that either have knowledge about outdoor nature recreation or disabilities.

Over time, including more actors in the expert network could support better visibility of individual needs within the system, bringing more flexibility in current rigid institutions, increase in resources and expertise regarding children with disabilities across the different actors and institutions in the system. Educating others and changing mindsets towards disabilities would promote strength and capability, encouraging proactive and inclusive attitudes, creating a supportive environment, shifting the 'school mindset' and fostering a belief in children's abilities, and promote independence and confidence (in both children and parents).

4. Wrap-up and plan for future workshops and activities

Wrapping up we decided to invite the Norwegian Trekking Association (DNT) and a communications expert into our expert network for the next workshop.

WORKSHOP 3: MONITORING AND INDICATORS

Date: 04.03.2024

Duration: 2.5 hours

Number of participants: 11 people

Profile of participants: Four peer-mentors living in or close to Oslo, Norway, one of them a parent of a child with disabilities, all with experience from camps for children, youth, or adults with disabilities. Three representatives from the Norwegian Trekking Association (DNT). One young activity leader from OOF. One communications person, one social science researcher and one natural science researcher from NINA.

Agenda:

1. Welcome and consent forms
2. Sharing of experiences from working with inclusive, organised outdoor nature recreation activities
3. Discussion on communication target group and other things to consider
4. What could indicators of change be?
5. Wrap-up

1. Welcome and consent forms

Everyone was welcomed. We had a short round of introductions for the newcomers. Consent forms were shared and signed.

2. Sharing of experiences from working with inclusive, organised outdoor nature recreation activities

The Norwegian Trekking Association (DNT) gave us an introduction to how they work with inclusive activities, centrally. Then a local DNT chapter gave us insights into how they work with inclusive, organised activities for people with disabilities.

DNT consist of 56 independent member organizations (local chapters) - for volunteers. Some member associations have no employees, others - such as Oslo - have more employees than DNT centrally. This means that there are a lot of people in DNT, but not necessarily a lot of control. As an example, DNT centrally cannot necessarily tell their local member organisations how things should or should not be. The member organisations in Drammen and Haugesund were the first to make offers for people with disabilities. The member organisation in Haugesund works mostly with offers for people with developmental disabilities. The member organisation in Drammen started a larger project that has become national – “mobility impairment and impaired vision”. Over the years DNT has had close collaboration with The Norwegian Association for Persons with Intellectual Disabilities (NFU) and they have cooperated with the Norwegian Association of the Blind and Partially Sighted - NABP. At national level there are however no organised outdoor nature recreation activities for people with disabilities as activities take place in the local member organisations. Most large associations have an established offer for developmentally disabled people and people with reduced mobility. Everyone is welcome, but it is important to describe

how the offer is organised. There are few offers for people in wheelchairs. DNT supports the idea to open the Act relating to Motor traffic on uncultivated land and in watercourses to include exceptions for people with reduced mobility so that they can get out into nature. DNT should be for everyone, and a main focus is on low-threshold offers that are easy to implement for the volunteers. It is not difficult to get volunteers in the organization involved in new cool things, but it is difficult to get volunteers to commit to low-threshold regular offers.

3. Communication: target group and other things to consider

We had a short discussion about communication and dissemination led by our communication person from NINA. She gave us many solid tips to think of in terms of target group, format, platform, etc.

4. What could indicators of change be?

Based on the discussions we had we thought that two indicators of change could be:

- Increase in number of organised activities inclusive of children and young people with disabilities over time
- Increase in number of contact points between outdoor voluntary recreational organisations and interest organisations for children and young people with disabilities

After the 3rd workshop in the expert network, we got some suggestions for additional indicators suggested from Patricia Ofori-Amanfo, Check Globe. These additional indicators are presented in the figure below (Fig. 3).

Additional indicators

Patricia Ofori-Amanfo, Check Globe

PLANET4B

- Increase in nature recreation centres with easy accessibility for people with disability.
- Increase in number of adults with disability engaging in nature recreation activities.
- Increase in number of children with disability engaging in nature recreation activities.
- Increase in nature recreation activities tailored or adapted for children/adults with disability.
- Active involvement of children/adults with disability in planning and decision-making concerning siting, creation and design of nature recreation areas.
- Increasingly readily and easily accessible information at vantage points for people with disability providing guidance and help on visiting nature recreation areas and engaging in activities.

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Figure 3. Additional indicators of change for the Oslo outdoor nature recreation case, developed by Patricia Ofori-Amanfo, Check Globe.

5. Wrap-up

Wrapping up we decided to follow up possibilities for working with the DNT local member organisation. We decided to have our next meeting in the expert network towards the end of April.

WORKSHOP 4: BARRIERS & OPPORTUNITIES FOR BROADER CHANGE

Date: 25.06.2024

Duration: 2.5 hours

Number of participants: 7 people

Profile of participants: Three peer-mentors living in or close to Oslo, Norway, aged 27-32 years, all with experience from camps for children, youth, and adults with disabilities and one with experience from serving on a political advisory board for people with disabilities. An activity leader and the manager of OOF. One social science researcher and one natural science researcher from NINA.

Agenda:

1. Welcome
2. Information on how the expert network meetings have informed the research under the Oslo outdoor nature recreational case study.
3. Today's workshop is our fourth and last meeting in the expert network, what is next?
4. Potential broader impact of the interventions.
5. Wrap-up and closing of meeting.

1. Welcome

Everyone was welcomed to our last and closing workshop in the expert network.

2. Information on how the expert network meetings have informed the research under the Oslo outdoor nature recreational case study.

The researchers in the expert network had the impression that the purpose and outcome of the workshops often had been very diffuse to the other members. Therefore, we set aside time for summarising the discussions that we had had in our previous three workshops and to give some concrete examples of what these discussions and exchanges of information had meant to our work outside of the workshops. To put the workshops into a greater context we gave the expert network a couple of examples from the other activities we also had in our case study. We mentioned the National survey sent to parents about their children's outdoor activities and the focus group interviews that we had with national and local outdoor nature recreation organisations.

The National survey about children's outdoor activities is sent to Norwegian parents every few years. In the last round (2022/3), we were allowed to include a question about whether the children had a disability. As an example of a finding that stood out from the survey, and which builds up under some of the themes discussed during the expert network workshops, we mentioned that parents of children with disabilities to a greater extent than other parents reported on a lack of a social networks as a barrier for outdoor nature recreation.

We told the expert network of how our conversations with them had been pivotal in terms of setting the scope for our focus group interviews, both in terms of the profile of actors that we interviewed and the topics that we covered but also in relation to how we understand the material. Among the important preliminary findings from these interviews, we see a clear need for more contact and a better flow of information and knowledge between classical outdoor nature recreation organizations and organisations that are experts on disabilities and in facilitating outdoor nature recreation for people with disabilities. Many outdoor nature recreation organizations wish to be inclusive of people with disabilities but feel insecure about how to do so or of what is needed. There is a need for role models and people that can "show the way" in these organisations. The mentoring scheme of Sunnaasstiftelsen can be an example for classic outdoor nature recreation organizations to follow and we think that outdoor nature recreation organisations should actively try to recruit their own mentors.

Putting the expert network meetings into the context of our wider work, sharing results and insights into how the experts in our network have helped guide our activities and our understanding of the data material that we have collected, was greatly appreciated. The experts in our network said they were glad to learn of how these meetings had informed and shaped our work. They said that they had wondered and felt uncertain about how our meetings had contributed to the goal of making outdoor nature recreation

experiences more accessible to children with disabilities. They were glad to learn about the concrete examples we gave them as much of the work in the expert network had felt fleeting or abstract.

3. Today's workshop is our fourth and last meeting in the expert network, what is next?

Extending on the concrete examples of how the expert network had informed and directed the work under the Norwegian case study, OOF gave a short presentation of how contributions from the expert network and findings from our other activities (will) influence and inspire their work.

OOF is a member organisation for outdoor nature recreation organisations. Their members include municipalities, voluntary organizations such as DNT and others. OOF was established 1936 and work for "outdoor nature recreation for all". As an example, OOF were early to work for the inclusion of immigrants in Norwegian outdoor nature recreation.

Findings from the current project (e.g. from the national survey, the focus group interviews, participatory observations, etc.) will be used by OOF for inspiration and to influence how they work with the inclusion of people with disabilities in outdoor nature recreation activities. OOF has many meeting points with different actors and a large contact network within their field of action. These connections can be used for disseminating information and findings from our project, for example, through courses that OOF holds for teachers, activity leaders, and others.

Among the many things that OOF do, they also manage an activity centre at Frognerseteren, bordering the Oslo municipality forests. OOF has a vision to transform this into a multi-purpose centre. Thus OOF took the opportunity to ask the experts in our expert network for input on how to make this possible. Some of the suggestions that came up are presented in the following three bullet points:

- Put up signs for wheelchair friendly paths.
- Indicate suitable places for setting up hammocks to rest or sleep outside. At the right height, it works well for those in wheelchairs.
- Activities: Orientation. Sleep outside. Cycling tours. Sauna.

The experts invited OOF to contact them again to make a visit to Frognerseteren and give further inputs for developing the place into a multi-purpose centre. They also encouraged OOF to invite organisations for the visually impaired and other disabilities.

Next, we discussed another idea for building on our case study results and the expert network experiences for the year of outdoor nature recreation: 2025. This idea would be to organise a meeting at Frognerseteren.

Some of the questions that we discussed included "who we should invite?", "who might need training?", and "who could benefit from getting to know each other better and talking together more?". We thought about some organizations that may wish to start / expand on outdoor nature recreation activities that are inclusive of children and other people with disabilities, such as Sunnaasstiftelsen, Frambu, LOL stroke, or the Oslo council for people with disabilities. One goal of a meeting across expert associations on disabilities and voluntary outdoor nature recreation organizations could be to make the latter category aware that there are mentors and to make them think about hiring a mentor. We concluded that "Role models are important" and that "Personal stories are effective". Thus, we thought we could have organisations share their stories. We also thought of panel discussions and group discussions. The conversation then drifted toward a discussion on potential broader impact of these interventions.

4. Potential broader impact of our interventions.

Already in our first expert network meeting we concluded that interventions which make outdoor nature recreation experiences more accessible to people and children with disabilities also benefit many other societal groups. Organised activities for children and youth with disabilities would also make outdoor nature recreation experiences accessible to for example older people or people with small children in

strollers. Facilitation is not only for those with a disability, but entire families and groups of friends. Also, mentors can be for people other than those with disabilities, e.g. politicians in need of input on inclusive develop in specific areas. In short making good nature experiences accessible for children with disabilities would make good nature experiences more accessible for all. Breaking down barriers identified within our work, for example by bridging knowledge exchange between expert organisations on disabilities and outdoor nature recreation organisations through mentors, could excel the availability of inclusive, organised outdoor nature recreation offers for all.

5. Wrap-up and closing of meeting.

Wrapping up we asked the expert members of our network if they would like to be informed of future activities or outcomes from the Oslo outdoor nature recreation case study. The experts said that they would like to be informed about future project activities and outcomes. They also wished to be given opportunity to comment and give feedback on potential publications.

«Tusen, tusen takk» (Many thanks) to our expert network! These meetings have been extremely valuable to our work. Thank you for your time, the experiences and the insights that you have shared with us!